

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Mirzarayimova Zebiniso Mansurbek qizi

OILA HUQUQI VA OILA MUNOSABATLARI

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

zenodo

